

CHRONIC PROSTATITIS. DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the study of diagnostics and treatment of chronic prostatitis. Prostatitis is an inflammation of the prostate gland, which called the prostate. The prostate gland is a minor part male reproductive organs. It is located under the bladder, around his neck. The fact is that the urethra passes through the prostate, that is, the prostate is located around the urinary tube. As a result, when the prostate enlarges, the urinary tract is compressed, which interferes with the passage of urine.

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Factors contributing to the development of prostatitis:

- urethritis
- irregular sex life (leads to stagnation of secretions)
- sedentary and sedentary lifestyle (leads to stagnant phenomena in the prostate gland)
- weakened immunity (due to lack of vitamins in food, alcohol abuse, smoking, hypothermia, emotional overload)

Routes of infection into the prostate: the main routes of infection into the prostate:

- descending (occurs in inflammatory processes in the kidneys and bladder)
hematogenous (with inflammatory processes in the body in gastrointestinal tract, kidneys, lungs, carious teeth)
- lymphogenous (with inflammation of the rectum)
- ascending (urethrogenic) (penetration of infection from urethra)

The post-infectious stage (chronic) does not have clear time periods

boundaries and depends on the degree of anatomical disorders in the prostate (prostate gland). At this stage, the pathogen may not determined by laboratory tests, but the inflammatory process while it continues with chronic prostatitis, there may be no symptoms at all.

Therefore, it is very important to undergo preventive examinations to identify disease in the early stages. However, prostate inflammation can indicate the following symptoms. Symptoms of chronic prostatitis:

- Periodic pain in the perineum, above the pubis, in the groin area.
- Painful, frequent urination.
- Discharge from the urethra during defecation
- Weakening erection
- Changing the duration of sexual intercourse
- Change in sexual sensations
- Slight increase in temperature

Chronic prostatitis is characterized by long-term and persistent course, in some patients it occurs without clear clinical symptoms. Features of the disease and clinical course of prostatitis depend on many reasons:

- * phases of activity of the inflammatory process
- * duration of the disease
- * the degree of involvement of neighboring organs
- * in the pathological process, ongoing influence on the course of the disease sedentary lifestyle
- * irregular sexual intercourse, etc.

There are basic diagnostic criteria:

- Rectal (through the rectum) digital examination prostate gland. Prostatitis is indicated by pain, asymmetry and heterogeneous structure of the prostate gland.[2]
- Study of the secretion (juice) of the prostate gland. In favor prostatitis is indicated by an increase in the number of leukocytes in the secretion (juice) of the prostate gland. The secret (juice) is obtained as a result diagnostic massage of the prostate gland. Exploring the secret (juice) of the prostate gland is the most reliable diagnostic method prostatitis.
- Ultrasound examination (ultrasound) of the prostate gland.

This is not a very reliable method for diagnosing prostatitis. In the early stages prostatitis, ultrasound may not reveal any pathological changes. Moreover, the results of the method largely depend on the experience and qualifications of the doctor, performing ultrasound.

- CBC
- UA
- PCR diagnostics for detection of causative agents of chlamydia and ureaplasmosis
- bacterioscopy of urethral smears to detect gonococci
- urofluometry
- prostate biopsy

Treatment of prostatitis

In order for the treatment to be successful, it is necessary to comply several conditions. Firstly, a very important factor is qualifications urologist and the patient's trusting relationship with him, correct diagnostics and, of course, strict adherence to all deadlines undergoing procedures and accurately following the specialist's instructions. Patients are indicated for outpatient treatment, which can last up to 1.5 months.[3]

Main methods of treatment:

- * antibacterial therapy
- * alpha blockers
- * hormonal therapy
- * prostate massage
- * physiotherapy
- * transurethral microwave thermotherapy (TUMT)
- * transurethral needle ablation of the prostate (TUNA)
- * laser therapy
- * surgical treatment methods (prostatectomy)
- * electrical stimulation.

One of the common methods of treating prostatitis is electrical stimulation. The outcome of treatment largely depends on the type of the device and the doctor's ability to operate it. It's best if electrical stimulation is prescribed together with laser irradiation. Only in this case, you can count on a positive result.

Magnetotherapy

Almost never prescribed as an independent type of treatment magnetic therapy, only in addition to other procedures. Transferred absolutely painless with minimal risk.

Transrectal Ultrasound therapy is by far the most tested and widely used method. Virtually painless procedure with high percentage of favorable outcome, best combined with phonophoresis.[1]

Prostate massage

But finger massage of the prostate can lead to unwanted complications, especially if there are foci of purulent in the prostate gland infections or stones. The procedure is not particularly pleasant, most often painful. It is not advisable to perform it on an inflamed prostate gland.

As a result, the key to successful treatment is timely treatment. The sooner you go to the doctor (if you are concerned about symptoms, characteristic of a given disease), the more effective the treatment will be

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